

Marking Your Own Homework

Policy Recommendations - Part C

Meyyappan Saravanan Lakshmi

Introduction

Part A of this white paper identified critical weaknesses in the evidence usage in the National Waste Policy Action Plan 2024 (NWPAP)(DCCEEW,2024). Quantitative evidence gaps at the consultation and adoption stages along with qualitative concerns at the formulation and evaluation stages of the Australian Policy Cycle (DIISRTE,2012). Part B of this white paper consolidated fourteen peer reviewed studies to examine whether independent scientific evaluation mechanisms improve policy effectiveness , target achievement and transparency in OECD countries.The findings validated that independent evaluation consistently outperforms government self reporting. Though this effectiveness is subjective to institutional design and political context (Bauer et al.,2016; Nagel et al.,2023; Andresen et al.,2018).

Building extensively on these two findings , Part C of this white paper presents two evidenced based recommendations.

- 1) Establish a CSIRO led Independent Scientific Advisory Panel (ISAP) for the NWPAP to provide peer review, transparent methodology and easy access to reported evidence.
- 2) Mandate Independent Third Party Evaluation of NWPAP 2030 targets through external benchmarking and decomposition analysis on a biennial cycle basis.

These recommendations are evaluated through a 4x4 risk matrix to assess the risk of political resistance and institutional stagnation. These risks are well documented in the science policy literature presented in part B (Andresen et al.,2018; De Dona & Linke,2023). The risk matrix already has an established use in environmental policy risk assessment, this provides a solid framework to evaluate likelihood and consequences of identified risks (ISO 31000:2018). A 2x2 matrix is used in the case of scenario planning to test the resilience of both recommendations under uncertainty; this is a method widely applied in the sustainability field to anticipate complex drivers of change. (Wilkinson & Kupers,2013; Stucki, n.d.).

Recommendation 1 : Establish a CSIRO led independent scientific advisory panel (ISAP)

Claim : The NWPAP should establish an independent scientific advisory panel led by CSIRO to provide peer review of commissioned datasets, ensure transparent methodology and publish annual interpreted evidence reports accessible to the general public.

Evidence : Part B's rapid review presented evidence supporting that scientific advisory institutions (SAI's) with high vertical integration directly correlate with effective policy outcomes across OECD countries (Nagel et al.,2023). Bauer et al. (2016) presented strong empirical evidence of SAI efficiency and credibility across 11 countries and 30 working SAI mechanisms. Hunsberger et al. (2020) validated critical evidence that Canada's 2017 independent expert panel scored highest across all criteria for regulatory review quality. This has dropped significantly as the panel faced subsequent reduction in autonomy. This draws a parallel that NWPAP's current framework, where sole reliance on commissioned Blue environment data without any independence creates risks of confirmation bias and selective reporting (Part A white paper ; Hunsberger et al., 2020).

Reasoning : Part A's quality weaknesses (weakness 1 & 3) are addressed through an ISAP. Independent verification and replication of evidence is a cornerstone requirement for credible scientific evidence (Bocher & Krott, 2016). Combining peer review into the policy cycle at the consultation and formulation stages (DIISRTE,2012), the ISAP would transform the NWPAP's evidence from a single source dataset to a transparently verified source for policy action. The APS200 framework provides direct institutional precedent for this recommendation as it recommends using trusted advisors such as CSIRO to broker scientific advice on contested issues (DIISRTE, 2012). A detailed SMART framework application is provided in Appendix. (Table 1)

Recommendation 2 : Mandate Independent Third Party Evaluation of NWPAP 2030 targets

Claim : The Australian government should mandate biennial independent third party evaluations of all seven targets, employing tactics such as external benchmarking, decomposition analysis and cross jurisdictional comparison. This will replace sole reliance on internal self reporting alone.

Evidence : Part B's rapid review findings revealed that implementation gaps are consistently exposed through external evaluation compared to self reported data. Daraio et al.(2025) exposed systemic efficiency disparities among 65% of Italy's waste targets in 275 Italian municipalities; this was solely due to self-reported data. Korica and Gotvajn (2025) demonstrated that decomposition analysis identifies specific legislative drivers of the Croatian circular economy targets that wouldn't have surfaced because of self reporting. To add furthermore Compagnoni (2022) found that upstream eco design failures were missed due to internal reporting frameworks. Solis et al.(2025) identified that second order unintended effects aren't measured by the EU circular economy.

Reasoning : This recommendation draws parallel to Part A's quantitative weakness 2 and 4. The lack of evidence proving implementation gap and provision of raw, uninterpreted data. The NWPAP currently provides waste data through spreadsheets and online reports without any interpretation. This assumes viewers independently possess skills to analyse raw datasets (part A). By mandating external evaluation with decomposition analysis and benchmarking methodologies, this recommendation would ensure clear progress towards 2030 targets. This includes an ambitious requirement to divert 11 million tonnes of waste from landfill which will be promptly measured against rigorous independently verified standards rather than self reporting alone. A detailed SMART framework application is provided in Appendix.

Risk Assessment

Risk : Political Resistance and Institutional Stagnation. (with respect to recommendation 1)

One critical risk to the establishment of an ISAP is political resistance and institutional stagnation. Government departments may resist ceding authority to an external panel, particularly when those findings contradicted already established narratives. NWPAP's current evidence structure makes it irrefutable to consider this risk, this ultimately reflects on institutional preference for controlled information environments rather than transparent scientific scrutiny.

Tool: 4x4 matrix

The 4x4 matrix was the perfect fit for the purpose of risk assessment because it evaluates the likelihood and consequences of the risk through a systematic and standardised framework (ISO 31000:2018). Risk matrices are a widely used tool in policy and program evaluation to communicate various risk levels to the decision makers in an accessible visual format (Duijm,2015).

Application and Key findings

The risk of political resistance as Likely (3) in likelihood scale. Part B evidence presents that science based policy tensions are frequent across OECD contexts with Andresen et al. (2018) findings prove that SAC's become inefficient when political variables are involved. De Dona and Linke (2023) identifies clear boundaries set by science based policy to strengthen credibility but risk perceived legitimacy. The consequences were assessed as Major (3), as political resistance could render the ISAP advisory without any influence, effectively neutralising its purpose. The resulting rating of High (Appendix) indicates without any mitigation, the effectiveness of the recommendation is highly threatened.

Nonetheless, this risk can be mitigated to Moderate through three strategies.

- 1) Legislating the ISAP advisory mandate within the NWPAP framework
- 2) Publishing government responses to ISAP recommendations (Hunsberger et al., 2020)
- 3) Phased introduction aligned with the biennial review cycle to decrease the institutional disruption.

Mitigation would cause the residual risks to shift to Unlikely (2) x Major (3) = Moderate. This is well within the acceptable implementation threshold. Both recommendations remain viable, though some require mitigation strategies to ensure maximum policy action is being derived.

Possible Futures

Scenario planning is a structured foresight methodology that guides policy makers to examine how interventions may perform under complex and uncertain conditions (Wilkinson & Kupers, 2013). Scenario planning, unlike forecasting, develops multiple theories for possible futures based on the interaction with uncertainties (Stucki, n.d). This tool is particularly suited for both the recommendations on NWPAP as political and institutional variables are inherently uncertain.

Key elements and Scenarios

Two predetermined elements cements the analysis,

- 1) Australia's 2030 NWPAP targets remain legislatively committed with biennial reviews within the framework (DCCEEW, 2024).
- 2) Waste generation per capita remains high at approximately 2.88 tonnes per capita, creating a pressure for reform (DCCEEW,2024).

Two drivers that guide the direction of change,

- 1) The growing OECD trend toward institutionalised independent policy evaluation (Bauer et al., 2016; Nagel et al.,2023).

- 2) The biennial review cycle of NWPAP creating regular reform windows (DCCEEW,2024).

Two critical uncertainties form the scenario axes,

- 1) Political commitment towards evidence based policymaking (strong vs weak)
- 2) Institutional capacity for independent scientific oversight (high vs low)

Under the ‘Gold Standard’ (strong commitment , high capacity) both the recommendations thrive. The ISAP is well resourced and third party evaluations are meticulous. ‘Good Intentions , Thin Bench’ (strong commitment ,low capacity) this causes irregular implementation as political will without sufficient expertise will demonstrate recommendation 1 struggling to recruit qualified panel members. ‘Shadow Rigour’(weak commitment , high capacity) will present a scenario where scientific capacity exists but government sidelines findings, reports are potentially ignored. ‘Stalled Status Quo’ (weak commitment , low capacity) sees neither recommendation gain traction and business as usual causes missed 2030 targets without any real accountability.

Implications for recommendations

Scenario analysis reveals that recommendation 2 (mandatory third party evaluation) demonstrates greater resilience across all four futures. As external evaluations can proceed through existing academic and institutional channels. On the other hand recommendation 1 (ISAP) is more reactive to political context thriving under ‘gold standard’ and completely neutralized under ‘shadow rigour’. The early warning signal for the latter scenario would be that an advisory panel should be established without a comply or explain mandate. A major waste management crisis would be a wild card that will shift political commitment from weak to strong.

Conclusion

This white paper reveals that Australia's NWPAP 2024, while informed quantitatively in its early stages, exhibits major gaps in evidence use, transparency, peer review and independent verification of targets (Part A). Further the rapid review confirmed independent scientific mechanisms consistently improve policy efficiency across OECD countries, but heavily subdued by political powers and institutional design (Part B).Part C of the white paper concludes with a CSIRO led ISAP and mandating independent third art evaluations of the 2030 targets which offers an evidence based pathway to address the challenges faced in Part A and B. Scenario analysis reveals third party evaluation as a proven resilient recommendation. The risk matrix addresses the need for legislative safeguards. These recommendations built within the NWPAP will provide an opportunity to achieve 2030 targets.

Appendix

Table 1: SMART Framework

Recommendation 1: Establish a CSIRO led Independent Scientific Advisory Panel (ISAP)

SMART Element	Details	Evidence / Justification
Specific	Stakeholders: DCCEEW (implementation lead), CSIRO (panel host), State/Territory Environment Ministers (consultation), Blue Environment (data coordination). Scope: Independent peer review of NWPAP evidence base across all seven targets.	SAIs with clear institutional mandates demonstrate higher saliency and credibility (Bauer et al., 2016). APS200 recommends CSIRO as trusted advisor for scientific brokerage (DIISRTE, 2012).
Measurable	Targets: 100% of NWPAP commissioned data undergoes independent peer review by Year 2. Annual published evidence report with methodology appendix. KPIs: Number of datasets peer-reviewed; publication of annual interpreted report; stakeholder accessibility rating.	Hunsberger et al. (2020) measured review quality across criteria including independence, transparency and accessibility, providing a validated measurement framework.
Achievable	CSIRO has an existing capacity in waste and circular economy research. Initial panel draws on existing CSIRO staff supplemented by 2-3 external academic appointees.	Nagel et al. (2023) demonstrated functional SACs operate effectively across Germany and Japan with modest institutional investment when vertically integrated into policy structures.
Relevant	Directly addresses NWPAP's commitment to evidence-informed policymaking (Department of Industry, Science and Resources, 2024). Addresses Part A weaknesses 1 and 3. Aligns with APS200 framework strategies for strengthening evidence at consultation and formulation stages (DIISRTE, 2012).	De Dona & Linke (2023) confirmed independent advisory mechanisms improve policy credibility across OECD/EU contexts when appropriately positioned.
Time-Bound	Phase 1 (2025-2026): Establish ISAP terms of reference and appoint a panel during the next biennial review. Phase 2 (2026-2027): First peer review cycle; publish inaugural evidence report. Phase 3 (2027-2028): Full integration into NWPAP policy cycle with legislated advisory mandate.	The biennial review cycle built into NWPAP (DCCEEW, 2024) provides natural integration points. Hunsberger et al. (2020) demonstrated panel establishment is achievable within a single policy review cycle.

Table 2: Recommendation 2: Mandate Independent Third-Party Evaluation of NWPAP 2030 Targets

SMART Element	Details	Evidence / Justification
Specific	Stakeholders: DCCEEW (commissioning body), Independent evaluators (universities, CSIRO, accredited audit firms), State/Territory governments (data providers). Scope: Biennial independent evaluation of progress toward all seven NWPAP 2030 targets. Goal: Replace sole reliance on self-reported data with externally verified target assessments using decomposition analysis and cross-jurisdictional benchmarking.	Daraio et al. (2024) demonstrated external evaluation of 275 municipalities exposed disparities invisible to self-reporting. Korica & Gotvajn (2025) showed decomposition analysis identifies legislative drivers missed internally.
Measurable	Targets: 100% of NWPAP targets evaluated independently by 2028. Published evaluation reports with OECD benchmarking. KPIs: Number of targets independently evaluated per cycle; implementation gaps identified; percentage of evaluation recommendations adopted in subsequent policy revision.	Compagnoni (2022) and Solis et al. (2025) demonstrated that external evaluation identifies upstream failures and unintended effects that self-reporting misses, providing measurable gap identification.
Achievable	Australian universities and CSIRO have existing waste policy research capacity. Decomposition analysis and benchmarking methodologies are well-established. Funding: Estimated \$2-3M AUD per biennial cycle. The competitive tender process ensures cost efficiency.	Daraio et al. (2024) and Korica & Gotvajn (2025) successfully applied these methodologies in comparable OECD waste policy contexts with standard academic resources.
Relevant	Directly addresses NWPAP's acknowledgment that 2030 targets are off-track (DCCEEW, 2024). Addresses Part A weaknesses 2 and 4. Aligns with Australia's National Science Statement commitment to evidence-informed decision making.	Part B confirmed external evaluation improves target achievement and transparency compared to self-reporting across OECD contexts.
Time-Bound	Phase 1 (2025-2026): Develop evaluation framework and methodology standards. Issue tender for first evaluation. Phase 2 (2026-2027): Complete first biennial evaluation of all seven targets. Phase 3 (2028-2030): Embed mandatory evaluation into NWPAP governance. The second cycle informs the final push toward 2030 targets.	NWPAP's biennial review schedule (DCCEEW, 2024) provides integration points. 2025 start allows two full evaluation cycles before the 2030 deadline.

Figure 1: 4x4 Risk Matrix — Political Resistance and Institutional Stagnation (Recommendation 1)

Likelihood/ Consequence	Negligible (1)	Minor (2)	Major (3)	Catastrophic (4)
Almost Certain (4)	Medium	High	Extreme	Extreme
Likely (3)	Low	Medium	HIGH ★ Pre-mitigation	Extreme
Unlikely (2)	Low	Low	MODERATE ★★ Post-mitigation	High
Rare (1)	Low	Low	Medium	High

★ Pre-mitigation: Likely (3) x Major (3) = HIGH

★★ Post-mitigation: Unlikely (2) x Major (3) = MODERATE

Table 3: Risk Assessment Summary

Risk	Political resistance and institutional stagnation: Government departments resist ceding evaluation authority to external scientific panel.
Likelihood (Pre)	Likely (3) - SACs commonly face political resistance across OECD contexts (Andresen et al., 2018; De Dona & Linke, 2023).
Consequence	Major (3) - Could render ISAP advisory-only without binding influence, neutralising its purpose.
Rating (Pre)	HIGH
Mitigation	(1) Legislate ISAP advisory mandate within NWPAP framework; (2) Require published government responses ('comply or explain'); (3) Phased introduction aligned with biennial review cycle.
Rating (Post)	MODERATE - Unlikely (2) x Major (3) = Acceptable

Table 4: Scenario Planning Elements

Category	Element	Citation
Pre-determined Element 1	Australia's 2030 NWPAP targets remain legislatively committed with biennial reviews.	DCCEEW, 2024
Pre-determined Element 2	Waste generation per capita remains high (~2.88 tonnes), sustaining reform pressure.	DCCEEW, 2024
Driver 1	Growing OECD trend toward institutionalised independent policy evaluation.	Bauer et al., 2016; Nagel et al., 2023
Driver 2	NWPAP's biennial review cycle creates regular reform windows.	DCCEEW, 2024
Uncertainty 1 (X-axis)	Political commitment to evidence-based policymaking (Strong vs Weak).	Andresen et al., 2018
Uncertainty 2 (Y-axis)	Institutional capacity for independent scientific oversight (High vs Low).	Nagel et al., 2023

Figure 2: 2x2 Scenario Planning Matrix

	High Institutional Capacity	Low Institutional Capacity
Strong Political Commitment	"The Gold Standard" - Both recommendations thrive. ISAP is well-resourced with CSIRO leadership, third-party evaluations are rigorous and independently published.	"Good Intentions, Thin Bench" - Political will exists but expertise and funding gaps lead to patchy implementation. ISAP struggles to recruit qualified panellists. Third-party evaluations lack methodological rigour.
Weak Political Commitment	"Shadow Rigour" - Scientific capacity exists within CSIRO and academia but government sidelines findings. ISAP produces high-quality reports with no formal government response. Third-party evaluations are conducted but recommendations are not actioned. Public accountability pressure builds slowly.	"Stalled Status Quo" - Neither recommendation gains traction. NWPAP continues self-reporting via Blue Environment without independent oversight. Scientific advisory infrastructure remains unfunded.

References

- Andresen, S., Baral, P., Hoffman, S. J., & Fafard, P. (2018). What Can Be Learned from Experience with Scientific Advisory Committees in the Field of International Environmental Politics? *Global Challenges*, 2(9), 1800055. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.201800055>
- Bauer, A., Pregernig, M., & Reinecke, S. (2016). Enacting effective climate policy advice: institutional strategies to foster saliency, credibility and legitimacy. *Evidence & Policy*, 12(3), 341–362. <https://doi.org/10.1332/174426416x14712636744181>
- Compagnoni, M. (2022). Is Extended Producer Responsibility living up to expectations? A systematic literature review focusing on electronic waste. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 367, 133101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133101>
- Daraio, C., Di Leo, S., & Simar, L. (2024). Impact of a regulatory target and external factors on the waste efficiency of Italian municipalities. *Waste Management & Research*, 43(4), 580–592. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242x241262698>
- De Donà, M., & Linke, S. (2022). 'Close but not too close' – experiences of science-policy bridging in three international advisory organizations. *Critical Policy Studies*, 17(1), 82–100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2022.2028173>
- Hunsberger, C., Froese, S., & Hoberg, G. (2020). Toward 'good process' in regulatory reviews: Is Canada's new system any better than the old? *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 82, 106379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106379>
- Korica, P., & Gotvajn, A. Ž. (2025). Analyses of the efficiency of the circular economy policies regarding the composting of the biodegradable waste in Croatia. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 27(5), 3816–3835. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-025-02343-z>
- Nagel, M., Satoh, K., & Henry, A. D. (2023). Network analysis of scientific advisory committee integration in climate change policy: A comparison of Germany and Japan. *PLOS Climate*, 2(6), e0000222. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000222>
- Solis, M., Milios, L., Tonini, D., Hansen, S. F., Scheutz, C., & Huygens, D. (2025). An empirical exploration of the unintended effects of circular economy policies in the European Union: The case of textiles. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 54, 452–465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2025.01.021>
- Böcher, M., & Krott, M. (2016). *Science makes the world go round: Successful scientific knowledge transfer for the environment*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-34079-1>
- DCCEEW. (2024). *National Waste Policy Action Plan 2024*. Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water, Australian Government.

<https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/waste/publications/national-waste-policy-action-plan>

DIISRTE. (2012). APS200 project: The place of science in policy development in the public service. Department of Industry, Innovation, Science, Research and Tertiary Education, Australian Government.

Duijm, N. J. (2015). Recommendations on the use and design of risk matrices. *Safety Science*, 76, 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2015.02.014>

ISO. (2018). ISO 31000:2018 Risk management — Guidelines. International Organization for Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/standard/65694.html>

Stucki, M. (n.d.). 2x2 Scenario Planning Matrix: A step-by-step guide. Futures Platform. <https://www.futuresplatform.com/blog/2x2-scenario-planning-matrix-guideline>

Wilkinson, A., & Kupers, R. (2013). Living in the Futures. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://rolandkupers.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/06/Link-14.pdf>

AI Declaration

I acknowledge the use of generative AI in the preparation of this assessment. The use of AI is documented below in accordance with unit guidelines, and a full prompt log with outputs is provided as a separate file in the Moodle dropbox. Claude by Anthropic (<https://claude.ai>). I used Claude for generating structure suggestions, understanding core concepts, and submitting iterations of my draft to give tracked changes for grammar checking, clarity improvements, and structural feedback for the assessment.